

Tunable Thermoshrinkable Hydrogels for 4D Fabrication of Cell-Seeded Channels

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Fabricating hydrogel-based channels with diameters below 200 μm remains challenging in advanced in vitro modeling and tissue engineering. To address this challenge, thermoshrinkable hydrogels that undergo reversible isotropic dimensional changes with temperature are developed. A thermoresponsive polymer with methacrylate groups (PNH-MA) is synthesized from polyethylene glycol (PEG), N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM), and 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA), enabling photo-cross-linking and precise material tuning. PNH-MA hydrogels can shrink up to 90% in volume (50% in diameter) and remain transparent allowing cellular imaging. In a four-dimension (4D) fabrication strategy, channels seeded with proximal tubule epithelial cells are shrunk to reduce diameters. Using pin pull-out mold casting, channels of 120 and 410 μm diameters are shrunk to 65 and 200 μm , respectively. While needle injection is challenging for channels smaller than 200 μm , volumetric printing addresses this limitation. The shrinkage properties enable leak-proof perfusion, allowing cell seeding and continuous unilateral flow in channels as small as 100170 μm . PNH-MA polymers represent one of the few examples of low-viscosity resins successfully used for hydrogel volumetric printing of complex scaffolds. This study highlights the potential of PNH-MA hydrogels for scalable, high-precision tubular scaffold fabrication in advanced in vitro modeling.

their behavior, such as differentiation, maturation, and polarization.^[1–3] For this reason, many studies indicate that three-dimension (3D) in vitro models more effectively recapitulate native tissue function compared to their two-dimension counterparts.^[4–7] To generate such models, cells can be incorporated within specific 3D architectures using biomaterials. The obtained biomaterial-based constructs offer mechanical and structural support to the developing tissue and can guide cellular behavior through geometric patterns.

For kidney in vitro models, hollow microchannels are regarded as effective structures for mimicking the tubular system of the nephron,^[4,6–10] with proximal tubule (PT) dimensions ranging from 10 to 70 μm in internal diameter.^[11,12] Although some research groups have recently investigated the relationship between the curvature of half pipe scaffolds (convex/concave) and PT epithelial cell (PTEC) behavior,^[13,14] scarce information is currently available about the effect of full pipe curvature, as determined by its internal diameter, on cell function.

This lack of information is partly due to the limitations of fabrication technologies and the challenge of seeding cells at high density into hydrogel channels with diameters below 200 μm . Moreover, the channel diameter significantly affects shear

1. Introduction

Cells sense their microenvironment via mechanotransduction mechanisms and respond to geometrical cues by adapting

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stresses generated by unilateral flow, which can be introduced through continuous channel perfusion to simulate physiological conditions.

When utilizing 3D printing technology to pattern biomaterials, the maximum printing resolution denotes the smallest achievable feature size. This resolution is determined by many factors, including the type of printing technique, the hardware, and the ink/resin properties.^[15–18] Hydrogels can be employed as ink/resin, being interesting biomaterials due to their resemblance to the extracellular matrix, general cytocompatibility, and tunable properties. They consist of cross-linked networks of hydrophilic polymers that can retain a large amount of water. In the last decade, significant advancements have been achieved in the fabrication of tubular tissues, including kidney tubules and blood vessels.^[19–21] However, with the currently available technologies, obtaining centimeter-scale hydrogel scaffolds presenting hollow cell-seeded channels with diameters in the range of 10–70 μm remains a challenge.^[7,22] With high resolution printing techniques such as stereolithography, channels in bulk hydrogels with the desired range could be obtained.^[23] Also other fabrication techniques, such as coaxial extrusion printing can be employed to produce hollow tubular structures with thin hydrogel walls with diameters in the desired range.^[24,25] However, the injection of high-density cell suspensions post construct fabrication proved to be very challenging for channel/tubule diameters below 200 μm , unless implemented within a microfluidic device.^[22,24]

In recent years, on-demand shrinkable hydrogels have gained applicability in the field of advanced in vitro modeling and tissue engineering, addressing the limitations previously mentioned.^[26–31] Shrinkable hydrogels are stimuli-responsive materials that exhibit volume changes in response to various triggers, such as pH,^[32] light,^[33] temperature,^[27–31,34–37] or specific chemicals that interact with the hydrogel.^[26,38] Their potential lies in utilizing them as a postfabrication and/or postcell seeding method to reduce scaffold dimensions.^[39] When these materials are fabricated via 3D printers, the process of fabrication and subsequent shrinking is classified as 4D printing (the 4th dimension being time) and it is also referred to as “shrinking–printing”^[26] or “contraction fabrication.”^[27] In these cases, the shrinking mechanism relies on the partial expulsion of water from the hydrogel matrix, prompted by the external trigger that increases the hydrophobicity of the polymer network. In case of 3D covalently cross-linked networks, the polymer chains have limited ability to reorganize and accommodate a conformation change. As a result, they uniformly contract, causing the hydrogel to decrease in dimensions in all directions.

Among the mentioned triggers for shrinkage, temperature is particularly suitable for biological applications when maintained within a near-physiological range. Consequently, significant advancements have been made in the development of thermoresponsive hydrogels that facilitate a cytocompatible shrinking process. In most cases, NIPAM was used to confer thermoresponsiveness due to its convenient lower critical solution temperature (LCST) of $\approx 32^\circ\text{C}$. This means that poly(NIPAM) (PNIPAM) chains in water are soluble at low temperatures but will precipitate when heated above their LCST due to a shift from a hydrated coil state to a dehydrated globular state.^[40] It is important to note that NIPAM exhibits thermoresponsive properties only when it is in a polymeric state, PNIPAM. However, to ob-

tain thermoshrinkable hydrogels, PNIPAM alone is insufficient, as two additional conditions must be met: i) the presence of a hydrophilic component, such as gelatin, alginate, or polyethylene glycol (PEG), and ii) the formation of a covalently cross-linked polymer network. For example, using a triple channel microfluidic device, photo-cross-linked PNIPAM and alginate-based hydrogels were employed to obtain double-walled microtubes with thermally tunable diameter size to mimic blood vessels.^[41] In another study, PNIPAM-based hydrogels were employed to thermally tune the diameter size of channels in microfluidic devices.^[42]

A simple way to create thermoshrinkable hydrogels for biological applications is polymerizing NIPAM monomers with a methacrylated biopolymer like methacryloyl gelatin (GelMA).^[28,30,31,35] Following the addition of a photoinitiator, light irradiation initiates NIPAM radical polymerization and cross-linking by GelMA to yield shrinkable hydrogels, showing diameter reductions of $\approx 35\%$ upon incubation in aqueous solutions at 37°C . With the aim of developing models of the PT with channel diameters close to physiological dimensions, our group recently synthesized such hydrogel constructs by volumetric printing.^[31] Although this approach enabled us to obtain channels with diameter smaller than 100 μm after shrinking, seeding PTEC was achieved only into larger channels ($\approx 200 \mu\text{m}$ after shrinkage). Moreover, the shrunken hydrogels become cloudy upon temperature increase, possibly due to phase separation between the formed PNIPAM blocks and the gelatin component. This phenomenon significantly impaired microscopical imaging of the cell-laden channels and thus their further biological characterization.

The aim of this work was to develop a temperature-triggered shrinkable hydrogel with a tunable degree of shrinkage and no turbidity in its shrunken state, to overcome the aforementioned limitations. To achieve this, we synthesized an ABA triblock copolymer with thermoresponsive A blocks that are methacrylated to enable cross-linking, named poly(NIPAM-co-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA)/MA)–PEG–poly(NIPAM-co-HEA/MA), for short PNH–MA, illustrated in **Figure 1A**. This synthetic design enabled us to tune the degree of shrinkage by varying the polymer molecular weights and its degree of methacrylation (DM). We characterized the PNH–MA-based hydrogels by analyzing the gel formation, the mechanical properties and, most importantly, the shrinking process (**Figure 1B**). We assessed the cytocompatibility of both the material and the shrinking process by using conditionally immortalized PTEC (ciPTEC) seeded onto the surface of cylindrical hydrogels, monitoring viability and surface coverage over 14 days. To move toward physiologically relevant geometries and dimensions, we tested ciPTEC seeding into channels obtained via pin pull-out mold casting with diameters of 120 and 410 μm , prior to shrinking. We monitored cell viability and monolayer formation in the lumens over time after shrinkage. Ultimately, we assessed the printability of the material using the volumetric printer to fabricate 3D-printed shrinkable channels (**Figure 1C**). The scaffold was designed to take advantage of the shrinkage properties to seal the hydrogel inlet around plastic tubing, thus guaranteeing a leak-proof connection for channel perfusion. This strategy enabled cell seeding in the shrunken channels with possibility to apply continuous unilateral flow.

Figure 1. Overview of PNH-MA-based thermoshrinkable hydrogels and 4D printing process to generate cell-seeded microchannels for in vitro modeling applications. A) Synthesis and chemical structure of PNH-MA polymer. In blue the hydrophilic PEG mid-block, in orange PNIPAM-based thermoresponsive blocks in which HEA was randomly copolymerized, and in violet MA moieties. B) Schematic representation of PNH-MA cylindrical hydrogels formed via photopolymerization. When immersed in aqueous solutions at temperatures above their LCST, the hydrogels uniformly shrink triggered by the conformation change of the cross-linked thermoresponsive domains. C) Schematic representation of a PNH-MA hydrogel scaffold obtained via volumetric printing. After cell seeding inside the printed hollow channel, smaller channel dimensions are reached via shrinkage at physiological temperature.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of the Thermoresponsive Hydrogel Precursor

In this study, we synthesized an ABA triblock copolymer with thermoresponsive A blocks that are methacrylated to enable cross-linking, named PNH-MA (Figure 1A). Three key components were integrated into the polymer design: i) thermoresponsive domains based on PNIPAM, ii) a hydrophilic block based on PEG to ensure adequate hydration before and after shrink-

ing, iii) HEA monomers were copolymerized into the thermoresponsive domains to enable subsequent functionalization with methacrylate groups (MA) for photo-cross-linking. PNH-MA was obtained via a two-step synthesis. The synthesized polymers were characterized by $^1\text{H-NMR}$, size exclusion chromatography (SEC), and UPLC, and the cloud point (CP) temperature was measured. The results are reported in Figure 2A.

The first step involved the atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) of NIPAM and HEA from a bifunctional PEG macroinitiator to form the PNH polymer.^[43–45] As depicted in Figure 2B, maintaining the PEG block constant at 6 kDa, PNH with different

Figure 2. Polymer characterization and photorheological analysis. A) Characterization overview all the synthesized PNH and PNH-MA polymers. The polymers were named according to the obtained NIPAM-co-HEA/PEG mass ratio (4, 8, and 10) and their DM range being classified as low (L), medium (M), and high (H). B) Schematic representation of the different PNH polymers obtained by changing the PEG to monomers feed ratio. C) Schematic representation of the different PNH-MA polymers obtained by changing the DM. D) Effect of polymer DM on CP temperature. E) Storage moduli (G') of PNH-MA_{4,L} samples upon photo-cross-linking in the presence of 0.1 wt% LAP for polymer concentrations varying between 2.5 and 10 wt%. At time zero, these polymer samples were subjected to 60 s of light irradiation to initiate the polymerization reaction. F) G' plateau values of 5 wt% PNH-MA hydrogels after 60 s of light irradiation. $N = 3$, mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

NIPAM-co-HEA/PEG mass ratios were synthesized, of 4, 8, and 10, respectively, resulting in molecular weights ($M_{n,NMR}$) ranging from 30 to 72 kDa, with dispersity index (\bar{D}) values below 1.5, in line with previously reported similar triblock copolymers.^[43–45] Across all synthesized polymers, a NIPAM/HEA molar ratio of $\approx 88:12$ was attained, slightly deviating from the aimed molar ratio of 90:10. Furthermore, all PNH polymers exhibited CP temperatures of ≈ 30 °C, close to the CP observed for PNIPAM homopolymers.^[40]

The second synthesis step involved the functionalization of the hydroxyl moieties of HEA with methacrylic anhydride. PNH-MA polymers of various DMs (i.e., the percentage of methacrylated HEA groups) were obtained, categorized as high (85–87%), medium (43–59%), and low (30–36%), respectively (Figure 2C). As expected, the higher the DM, the more pronounced the decrease in cloud point temperature (Figure 2D and Figure S2A,B (Supporting Information)). Consistent with prior investigations,^[40] increasing the hydrophobicity of

PNIPAM-based chains leads to a decrease in the temperature at which the transition from coil to globule conformation occurs. Furthermore, in contrast to the sharp CP transition observed for PNH, the methacrylated polymers exhibited a gradual onset of clouding phenomena spanning a broader range of temperatures, likely attributable to variations of the DM within a PNH–MA batch.

2.2. Hydrogel Formation via Photo-Cross-Linking Reaction

We investigated the formation of hydrogels by irradiating aqueous solutions of PNH–MA containing lithium phenyl-2,4,6-trimethylbenzoylphosphinate (LAP) as a photoinitiator in cylindrical molds. Polymer concentrations ranging from 2.5 to 10 wt% were screened for hydrogel formation at different temperatures. At 4 °C, solutions with a polymer content above 3.5 wt% yielded hydrogels possessing adequate structural integrity by supporting their own weight when handled with a spatula without shape deformation. Conversely, pregel solutions below 3.5 wt% resulted in hydrogels too weak to maintain their form, despite demonstrating covalent cross-linking as confirmed by rheological frequency sweep measurements (Figure S2D,E, Supporting Information).

Additionally, it was noted that the temperature of the polymer solution significantly influenced the hydrogel formation. Solutions of different PNH–MA, each with varied CPs determined by the three DM ranges (Figure 2C), were subjected to cross-linking at temperatures of 4, 22, and 37 °C. Stable, transparent hydrogels with shape retention were obtained when the temperature remained below the CP during light exposure. By contrast, this result was not achievable when the temperature of the PNH–MA solution exceeded its CP (Figure S2C, Supporting Information). Adequate network formation is only effective below the LCST. Above this temperature, the relatively hydrophobic MA groups clustered as the polymer chains transition to their globular state and self-assemble in micelle conformations.^[44] This phenomenon might explain the formation of weaker gels when they were cross-linked above the CP.

To assess the efficiency of cross-linking, the residual nonreacted MA moieties were quantified for PNH–MA_{4,L} hydrogels (5 wt%) as representative samples. The findings revealed that over 97% of MA moieties were polymerized upon irradiation for 10, 20, and 60 s (Table S2, Supporting Information). Moreover, sol-fraction analysis revealed that over 95% of the polymer content was retained within the hydrogel network after cross-linking (Table S2, Supporting Information).

Rheological analysis was performed at 4 °C to assess the formation of PNH–MA gels following light exposure by varying the polymers wt%, DM, and number average molecular weight (M_n). In all cases, the storage moduli (G') rapidly increased, surpassing the loss modulus (G'' , not shown) and reaching maximum values within 60 s after starting the irradiation (Figure 2E and Figure S2F (Supporting Information)). Rheological data also showed that gels with a large range of G' values (from 25 to 3500 Pa) were obtained by varying the tested parameters. As expected, an increase in polymer concentration (wt%) and in DM, associated with a higher density of cross-linking sites, led to higher G' values. Additionally, polymers with higher M_n produced stiffer gels (Figure 2F).

2.3. Temperature-Triggered Shrinking Behavior of PNH–MA Hydrogels

Due to their thermoresponsive nature, cross-linked PNH–MA hydrogels exhibited the ability to shrink on demand when the temperature was increased above their CP (Figure 3A and Movie S1 (Supporting Information)). This shrinking behavior was investigated by incubating cylindrical-shaped hydrogels in aqueous buffered solutions at different temperatures. Currently, research in this field lacks a standardized methodology for reporting shrinkage characterization values, with different studies employing varying equations to calculate shrinkage. To enable a direct comparison of the shrinking properties of PNH–MA hydrogels with previous shrinkable hydrogels, we used two different equations to characterize the shrinking process: i) the shrinkage factor (x -fold reduction) defined as the ratio of the original gel dimensions to the shrunken dimensions, while ii) the shrinkage degree (%) as the percentage reduction in these dimensions. Furthermore, previous studies reported shrinkage values at times based on volume reduction,^[26,27,38] while others as reductions in area^[28] or in diameter.^[29,31,34] Importantly, the shrinkage process of PNH–MA hydrogels occurred isotropically, with an equivalent reduction in both the cylinder's diameter and height. In this study, we primarily reported shrinkage values based on diameter reduction. When comparing shrinking factors across different studies, it is crucial to consider that shrinkage values vary depending on whether they are expressed in terms of diameter, area, or volume reduction. This variation arises from the mathematical distinctions between measuring shrinkage in 1D, such as diameter or height, in 2D as area, or in 3D as volume. In other words, the definition and measurement of the hydrogel's dimensions significantly influence the calculated shrinkage. For example, for 5 wt% PNH–MA_{10,L} gels, we observed a twofold (50%), 4.5-fold (75%), and tenfold (90%) reduction in diameter, area, and volume, respectively (Figure S3A, Supporting Information). To facilitate more straightforward comparisons across studies, we propose standardizing the reporting of shrinkage values by expressing them as the percentage of diameter or height reduction. This approach is particularly relevant for research, such as the present study, that leverages shrinkage to enhance the resolution of hydrogel features.

Overall, the higher the incubation temperature, the higher the shrinkage degree of the gels (Figure 3B,C). This trend is in line with observations for other thermoshrinkable hydrogels.^[29,31] Depending on the NIPAM-co-HEA/PEG mass ratio of the polymer, the degree of the shrinkage varied among the tested temperatures. For polymers with a mass ratio of 4 (Figure 3B), the diameter reduction was observed above 30 °C, with higher shrinkage at higher temperatures. On the other hand, polymers with mass ratio of 10 (Figure 3C) showed partial shrinkage already at 22 °C ($\approx 15\%$) and similar degrees of shrinkage were reached at all temperatures above 30 °C ($\approx 50\%$). All gels reached their respective minimum dimensions within 6 h of incubation. Moreover, as is typical for temperature-induced shrinking,^[39] the dimensional changes were fully reversible by exposing the gels to temperatures above and below the LCST in a cyclic manner (Figure S3B,C, Supporting Information).

We examined the impact of various parameters on the extent of hydrogel shrinkage at 37 °C. Variations in the polymer

Figure 3. Overview of the temperature-driven shrinking properties of PNH-MA cylindrical-shape hydrogels. A) Timestamp pictures of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{10,L} hydrogels shrunken by being immersed in PBS at 37 °C. Scale bar = 1 cm. B,C) Diameter reduction over time of 5 wt% hydrogels of (B) PNH-MA_{4,L} and (C) PNH-MA_{10,L} incubated in PBS at different temperatures. D) Diameter reduction over time of PNH-MA_{4,M} hydrogels with different solid contents incubated in PBS at 37 °C. E) Diameter reduction of 5 wt% hydrogels with different NIPAM-*co*-HEA/PEG mass ratios incubated in PBS at 37 °C. F) Shrinkage degree (%) of diameter reduction after 24 h at 37 °C of 5 wt% hydrogels with different DMs. G) Compression moduli of 5 wt% PNH-MA hydrogels with varying NIPAM-*co*-HEA/PEG mass ratios, hence differing shrinkage degrees, in both their swollen (22 °C) and shrunken (37 °C) states. The shrinkage degrees were 38%, 47%, and 52% for PNH-MA with mass ratios of 4, 8, and 10, respectively. For all figure panels, $N = 3$, mean \pm SD.

NIPAM-*co*-HEA/PEG mass ratio exhibited the most pronounced effect, with the maximum degree of shrinkage attained at ratio of 10, resulting in a 50% reduction in diameter (Figure 3E,F). These results are in line with previous results,^[31] where a higher degree of shrinkage is observed at increased PNIPAM content. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was used to assess the compression moduli of the hydrogels in both swollen and shrunken states. While not eliciting significant differences in stiffness in the swollen states, variations in NIPAM-*co*-HEA/PEG mass ratios, and thereby the shrinking properties, notably impacted stiffness in the shrunken gels (Figure 3G). Consistent with prior re-

search findings,^[31] it was observed that larger degree of shrinkage correlated with increased stiffness at the shrunken state. This phenomenon can be explained by the polymer network densifying as water is expelled during the shrinkage process.

The solid content of the gel has a minor effect on the shrinkage capacity, although gels with a lower solid content achieved slightly smaller dimensions (Figure 3D). In line with previous results,^[26,31] this trend can be explained by a less dense thus more flexible network implying that the hydrogels can more efficiently expel water. Regarding compressive analysis, as expected, higher polymer contents led to notable increases in compression

moduli for both swollen and shrunken states (Figure S3E, Supporting Information).

The DM played an effect on the shrinking properties only for the highly methacrylated polymers (DM 85–87%) giving less room for conformational changes (Figure 3F). In addition, hydrogels with high DM turned slightly opaque after photo-cross-linking and entirely turbid at 37 °C, while hydrogels with low to medium DM consistently remained transparent. A high concentration of hydrophobic side groups along the polymer backbone may lead to the formation of microdomains enriched in hydrophobic moieties, which tend to phase-separate from water. This phenomenon can cause light scattering, resulting in the turbidity effect. In addition, as previously reported in Section 2.2, higher DM led to a decrease in the CP temperature, which may explain the different visual appearance and shrinking properties. Moreover, hydrogels cast at temperatures close to their CP exhibited reduced shrinkage compared to those cross-linked at temperatures below their CP (Figure S3D, Supporting Information).

PNH–MA hydrogels incubated in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) exhibited no signs of degradation, as indicated by the absence of weight changes, for a duration of at least 30 days in both their swollen and shrunken states (Figure S3F, Supporting Information). The only change in gel weight occurred during the first 24 h of incubation at 37 °C, attributed to water expulsion and shrinkage. By weighing the gels, it was possible to calculate the residual water content of shrunken hydrogels. For example, 94% water content was registered for swollen 5 wt% PNH–MA_{4,L} hydrogels, which decreased to 76% after 24 h shrinking at 37 °C. Clearly, the hydrogels remain rich in water, despite the significant size reduction. As the hydrogel undergoes shrinkage and water is expelled from the matrix, the relative polymer content increases, suggesting a decrease in the pore size of the hydrogel network.

2.4. Cytocompatibility of Thermoshrinkable PNH–MA Hydrogels

PTECs cover the lumen of the PT, forming a tight barrier that enables reabsorption of water and solutes, and secretion of metabolic waste. In vitro models of the PT utilizing ciPTEC focus on replicating the leak-free monolayer at the matrix–medium interface.^[3,10,46] CiPTECs are cultured at 33 °C to maintain a proliferative state until they reach ≈90% confluency, and are subsequently transferred to 37 °C to enable maturation.^[47] To evaluate the cytocompatibility of the newly developed shrinkable material, ciPTECs were seeded onto the surface of cylindrical PNH–MA hydrogels, and cell viability and surface coverage were monitored over a period of 14 days. Hydrogels at a polymer content of 5 wt% were tested for PNH–MA_{10,L} (Figure 4) and PNH–MA_{4,M} (Figure S4, Supporting Information), exhibiting respective shrinkage in diameter of 50% (high shrinkage) and 35% (low shrinkage) at 37 °C.

As expected, due to the lack of cell binding domains of PNH–MA polymers, ciPTEC did not adhere to the surface of pristine gels (Figure 4B). To introduce bioadhesive sites on the gel surface, a 3,4-dihydroxy-L-phenylalanine (L-DOPA) coating and a double coating of L-DOPA and collagen type IV (ColIV) were tested. Both coatings have been utilized in previous studies for ciPTEC culture on inert scaffolds.^[48,49] CiPTEC seeded onto coated gels adhered to the surface, exhibiting viability values com-

parable to those of the control group, i.e., ciPTEC seeded onto treated plastic (2D control) (Figure 4D and Figure S4D (Supporting Information)). Interestingly, while high viability (>85%) was observed at days 3 and 14, a slight drop in viability values was noticed at day 7 for both ciPTEC seeded onto coated gels and for the 2D control group. This drop might be caused by the transition from proliferative to maturation state of the cells after being moved to 37 °C at day 4. Since no difference was observed between the two screened coating types, the single L-DOPA coating was selected for further experiments, being cheaper and simpler than the double coating. Moreover, no difference in shrinkage degree was measured between pristine and coated gels, with similar shrinkage observed for gels incubated in both PBS and culture medium (Figure S4B,C, Supporting Information).

The shrinking process occurred without exerting detrimental stress on the cells, ensuring their adhesion and viability remained unaffected. As illustrated in Figure 4A, to assess whether the shrinkage of PNH–MA gels induced by successive temperature steps affects the stability of the coating layer, cell adhesion, and cell viability, we compared cells seeded on swollen gels (Group A) with those on gels preshrunk at 33 °C (Group B). In the latter case, no dimensional change occurred during coating application and cell attachment, unlike the former case. After adding the cell suspension to the gels, a few hours are generally required for the cells to adhere to the surface. The same amount of time is required for the gels to shrink and reach their minimum dimensions (Section 2.3 and Figure 3B). No differences in viability and cell adhesion were observed at any measured time point between gels that underwent significant shrinkage during cell attachment (Group A) and those that did not change in dimensions during cell seeding (Group B). Overall, the results indicated that the temperature-triggered shrinking process did not have an effect on the coating and resulting cell adhesion and viability.

2.5. Cell-Seeded Shrinkable Channels Obtained via Casting

To more accurately replicate the physiological environment of the proximal tubule, ciPTEC were seeded into PNH–MA hydrogel channels obtained via pin pull-out mold casting. Briefly, the gels were cast around needles (outer diameter (O.D.) 413 μm) or wires (O.D. 120 μm), which were removed after polymerization to create hollow, straight channels with the corresponding diameters (Figure 5A). Using a syringe needle (Figure 5B), the channels were perfused to apply the L-DOPA coating to their internal walls, followed by cell seeding inside the channels (Figure 5D). After the cells adhered to the internal walls, proliferation conditions (33 °C) were maintained until ≈80% confluency, then the gels were moved to 37 °C to enable cell maturation. The timing for the temperature switch varied among each performed experiment, depending on the success of the cell seeding and adhesion inside the used channels. Cell viability and internal wall coverage were monitored over time using live/dead staining (Figure 5C). Importantly, (confocal) imaging was feasible because the gels remained transparent, allowing the laser to easily penetrate the bulk hydrogel and reach the channels, unlike previously reported PNIPAM-based shrinkable hydrogels.^[28,31]

For the needle channels with an initial diameter of ≈410 μm, the cell seeding procedure was successful. After the successive

A) Group A (volume change after cell seeding)

Group B (no volume change after cell seeding)

Figure 4. CiPTEC seeded onto cylindric hydrogels of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{10,L} (high shrinkage properties). Refer to Figure S4 (Supporting Information) for PNH-MA_{4,M} samples (low shrinkage properties). A) Schematic representation of the experimental workflow. To investigate whether the shrinkage might affect the stability of the coating layer, cell adhesion, and cell viability, cells were seeded onto swollen gels (Group A) and gels that were preshrunk at 33 °C (Group B). B) Confocal microscopy images of the top surface of ciPTEC-seeded hydrogels stained with calcein AM (live/green) and propidium iodide (PI, dead/red). Scale bars 200 μm. For the images of pristine gels, bright field images are shown along with the fluorescent signals for gel visualization. C) Dimensional changes of the hydrogels in Groups A and B monitored during cell culture experiments. Gels were kept in PBS until day 0, then moved to culture medium. The shrinkage was induced by the successive temperature incubation steps. *N* = 3 (mean ± SD). D) Viability quantification of ciPTEC seeded onto coated PNH-MA hydrogels of both Groups A and B, and 2D control group. *N* = 3, mean ± SD. The 2D control group consisted of ciPTEC seeded into culture plates.

Figure 5. Cell-seeded shrinkable channels obtained by mold casting. A) Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) mold for gel casting with needles (O.D. 413 μm) or wire (O.D. 120 μm). The gels were cast around the needles/wires, which were subsequently removed to create hollow, straight channels with the corresponding diameters. B) Example of channel perfusion via manual injection: L-DOPA solution injected into swollen wire-based channels. C) Viability and internal wall coverage values of cell-seeded needle channels of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{10,L}. In this experiment, ciPTECs were cultured at 33 °C for 9 days to reach $\approx 80\%$ confluency, then moved to 37 °C for further 7 days. $N = 3$, mean \pm SD. D) Bright field images of the cell seeding process for needle channels made of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{10,L} (high shrinkage). Scale bars = 500 μm . E) Confocal microscopy images of cell-seeded needle channels made of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{10,L} (high shrinkage) stained with calcein AM (Live/green) and PI (Dead/red). Scale bars = 200 μm . Z-stack shown as MAX intensity overlay. F) Diameters of cell-seeded needle channels at the different temperatures. The dotted line represents the maximum value of PT diameters.^[12] G) Bright field images of the cell seeding process for wire-based channels made of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{4,M} (low shrinkage). Scale bars = 100 μm . H) Confocal microscopy image of cell-seeded wire channel made of 5 wt% PNH-MA_{4,M} (low shrinkage) stained with calcein AM (Live/green) and PI (Dead/red). Scale bar = 100 μm . Z-stack shown as MAX intensity overlay. I) Diameters of wire channels at the different temperatures. The dotted line represents the maximum value of PT diameters.^[12]

incubation steps at 33/37 °C, the cell-laden channels shrank to minimum diameters of ≈ 210 and $280 \mu\text{m}$ when PNH-MA_{10,L} (high shrinkage) and PNH-MA_{4,M} (low shrinkage) were used, respectively (Figure 5E,F). On the other hand, although the application of the L-DOPA coating was successful for the $120 \mu\text{m}$ wire channels, as indicated by the darkening of the channels (Figure 5B), cell seeding was less successful (Figure 5G–I). As shown, few cells were present inside the wire channels after injection of the cell suspension, with high heterogeneity among samples. This heterogeneity can be attributed to the fact that the smallest needle used for the injections had an outer diameter of $200 \mu\text{m}$, which was nearly twice the diameter of the channels. As previously reported,^[7] it proved to be very challenging to seed cells at high density in channels with diameters below $\approx 200 \mu\text{m}$.

For the needle channels that facilitated satisfying cell seeding, cells were clearly adhering to the internal walls (Movie S2, Supporting Information) and the channels remained open throughout the 16 days culture period. Cell viability remained high (>85%) in their proliferative state (33 °C) and, as expected, slightly dropped (70–85%) after the channels were moved to 37 °C. This caused a loss of confluency in the lumens. Interestingly, while the cell layer cultured onto the hydrogel disks could bridge the formed gaps (see previous section), complete monolayer recovery in the channels was not observed, showing a constant decrease in surface coverage over time. This phenomenon may be attributed to the repeated manual injections into the channels for medium refreshing and immunostaining. The resulting high shear stresses likely contributed to cell detachment and disruption of the cell layer. While this effect may not have been observed in cells maintained at 33 °C due to their active proliferative state, it became apparent at 37 °C, where the cells were unable to repopulate the channel walls following the repeated injections administered every 2–3 days. To address this issue, future experiments using needle channels may consider gently rocking the gel to induce mild medium flow within the channel, thereby reducing the need for manual injections post-cell seeding.

Although successful for channels with diameters ranging from 210 to $400 \mu\text{m}$, the repeated manual injections of this experimental set up were detrimental to the growing cell layer, causing cell detachment and loss over time. Thus, a confluent layer at the maturation temperature of 37 °C was never achieved with this strategy. Moreover, since seeding cells into channels smaller than $200 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter proved to be not feasible by manual injection, we tested alternative strategies. These included cell seeding by rocking the gels immersed in a high-density cell suspension (5×10^6 cells mL⁻¹), or by placing a drop of cell suspension onto the entrance of the vertically oriented channels (in air) to allow diffusion via capillary forces. However, both methods were unsuccessful (results not shown).

2.6. Volumetric Printing of PNH–MA Shrinkable Hydrogels

To address the limitations of the mold-cast channel strategy as discussed in Section 2.5, we opted to change the fabrication method by utilizing volumetric printing as a 3D printing technique. Volumetric printing is a light-based high-speed printing technology that generates 3D objects in a layer-less fashion, as

opposed to conventional layer-by-layer 3D printing.^[50,51] A digital micromirror device shapes (visible) light into filtered back projections of the object to be printed, as instructed by a tomographic reconstruction algorithm. The projections are sent to a rotating volume of a photoresponsive material at specific angles, and the resulting light dose accumulation allows for selective cross-linking of the resin into the desired 3D object. In contrast to mold casting, which has limited design capabilities, particularly for hollow channels, volumetric printing enables the fabrication of small hydrogel channels with scaffold designs that facilitate perfusion through the incorporation of channel inlets.

PBS solutions of PNH–MA containing LAP as photoinitiator were used as photocurable resin for volumetric printing (Figure 1C). First, we assessed the volumetric printability of various PNH–MA-based solutions, by screening the effect of polymer content, DM, and M_n on shape fidelity and resolution. Maintaining consistent printing conditions, all PNH–MA-based resins successfully yielded prints with a positive resolution range of 222 – $633 \mu\text{m}$, with the lowest values within the concentration range of 5–7.5 wt% (Figure S5, Supporting Information). Consistent with previous studies,^[18,51] we observed that achieving the highest resolution requires adjusting the light dose according to the CAD model, polymer type, and ink composition. Importantly, PNH–MA solutions required to be printed at 4 °C to ensure adequate cross-linking (Section 2.2). Taking into account the influence of the screened parameters on shrinking properties (as discussed in Section 2.3), the optimal resin selected for further experiments was a 5 wt% solution of PNH–MA_{10,L}. Upon optimized printing conditions, we successfully volumetrically printed hydrogels with complex geometries, focusing specifically on models presenting hollow channels (Figure 6B).

Similarly to cast hydrogels, the printed hydrogels underwent uniform shrinkage upon increasing the temperature above the LCST (Figures 6 and S6 and Movie S1 (Supporting Information)). In addition, the printed hydrogels retained high shape fidelity also during the reversed swelling process, and the shrinking/swelling could be cycled many times without signs of shape deformation. Importantly, when channels were present, they remained open. Upon quantitative analysis, the shrinkage degrees were similar for all the analyzed segments and comparable to cast hydrogels (Figure 6C). These results suggested that the shrinkage occurred in an isotropic fashion, independent of the initial shape or volume of the scaffolds (Section 2.3).

This study represents one of the few examples demonstrating the successful use of low-viscosity resins for hydrogel volumetric printing of complex shapes like gyroids or microchannels. Until recently, a fundamental requirement for biomaterial-based resins has been having high viscosity or existing in a physically cross-linked gel state during printing. It is generally thought that printing liquid inks would fail as the forming hydrogel would sink due to gravity during the vial rotation. For this reason, most of the currently used hydrogel inks for volumetric printing are based on mammalian gelatin, which shows a convenient thermoreversible gel state at 4 °C.^[52] Nevertheless, we achieved successful printing of several complex shapes using PNH–MA-based resins, which shows low viscosity at printing conditions (see the Supporting Information for viscosity values). This success can likely be attributed to the faster cross-linking reactions, which result from the higher concentration of MA

Figure 6. Volumetric printing of PNH–MA thermoshrinkable hydrogels. A) 3D-printed compass-shape hydrogel undergoing (reversible) shrinking process upon temperature increase. B) CAD models and 3D reconstructions obtained via light sheet reconstruction of 3D-printed gyroid and scaffold with two curved channels, in their swollen and shrunken states, respectively. C) Dimensions of cast and 3D-printed hydrogels in their swollen and shrunken states. Shrinkage degrees were calculated and reported as percentages of dimension reduction ($N = 3$, mean \pm SD). For all, printing resin: 5 wt% PNH–MA_{10,L} and 0.25 wt% LAP in PBS at 4 °C. Light doses ranged between 120–200 mW cm⁻², corresponding to printing times of 12–20 s.

moieties present in our polymer backbone compared to gelatin-based resins. For gelatin-based materials, the amino groups of lysine side chains are typically functionalized with photo-cross-linking moieties, with a maximum functionalization level of ≈ 0.3 mmol g⁻¹ of polymer.^[18,53] All of the PNH–MA polymers used in this study exhibited a higher concentration of MA groups, ranging from 0.33 to 1.04 mmol g⁻¹ (Figure 2A). This increased MA content resulted in faster polymerization reactions with high conversion, as evidenced by photorheological characterization.

2.7. Cell-Seeded Microchannels Obtained via Volumetric Printing

To overcome the aforementioned limitations regarding cell seeding in channels of diameters below 200 μ m, hollow channels incorporated into a PNH–MA-based scaffold with a specific design^[54] were fabricated via volumetric printing (Figure 7A,B). The scaffold design featured an inlet pocket that enables permanent connection to a plastic tube by accommodating a sealing rubber ring (Figure 7C). We capitalized on the shrinking properties of PNH–MA material to seal the hydrogel inlet around the rubber ring via shrinking at 33 °C, enabling a leak-proof connection between the tube and the channel, along with the reduction of the channel diameter (Figure 7D). The whole construct could then be perfused by connecting it to a syringe through the plastic tube (Figure 7E and Movie S3 (Supporting Information)). With this setup, the repetitive injections needed for L-DOPA coating, cell seeding, and medium refreshment were less disruptive to the integrity of the channels compared to needle injections, as the ab-

sence of a needle preserved the smoothness and intactness of the channel surface (Figure 7F).

This scaffold design combined with the shrinking properties of PNH–MA material enabled easy perfusion and successful cell seeding into hydrogel channels with a diameter range of 100–170 μ m (Figure 7G–J). This strategy enabled, for the first time, cell seeding into hydrogel channels with diameters below 200 μ m—a significant challenge acknowledged across the field and supported by the previously discussed results achieved through pin pull-out mold casting (Section 2.5). During cell seeding, although perfusion of the cell suspension through the channel was straightforward, residual microflows within the channel caused cells to either flow back toward the inlet area or leak toward the outlet. This hindered effective cell retention within the channel until adhesion was achieved. This phenomenon was previously observed where cells were seeded into hydrogel channels or tubular structures.^[26] We solved this issue by temporarily keeping the cell-perfused channels in a horizontal orientation within a dry, humidified environment until cell adhesion occurred. The cells that adhered on the channel surface remained viable over 10 days (Figure S7, Supporting Information), covering the channel surface over time in their proliferative state. The channel lumen remained open, as shown in the cross-sections of Figure 7I,J and in Movie S4 (Supporting Information).

To demonstrate the potential to introduce unidirectional continuous flow to more closely recapitulate the physiological conditions of the PT, the shrunken cell-free scaffold was placed in a custom-made reservoir and connected to a peristaltic pump in a close loop. Then, continuous perfusion of PBS was applied at

Figure 7. Scaffold design^[54] for volumetric printing of hydrogel-based microchannels presenting an inlet that enables a leak-proof connection to plastic tubing after shrinkage. This innovative design enabled easy perfusion and cell seeding into channels with diameter below 200 μm . A) Scaffold CAD design with channel diameter of 250 μm . B) 3D-printed 5 wt% PNH-MA_{10,L} hydrogel. C) Manual insertion of a plastic tube and rubber ring into the inlet pocket of the swollen hydrogel. D) Shrunken hydrogel (33 °C) sealing the ring to generate a leak-proof connection between the tube and the channel. E) Perfusion of the channel with a purple dye solution after connecting the tube to a syringe. F) Microscopy image of the dye-perfused channel. Scale bar 1 mm. G) Channel diameters after printing, before (3 h at RT) and after connection to the tube (24 h at 33 °C). Values reported for three different batches of 3D-printed scaffolds. The dotted line represents the channel diameter of the CAD model (250 μm). H) Confocal microscopy image of ciPTEC seeded into the shrunken channel (day 7, 33 °C), stained with calcein AM (green, live) and PI (red, dead). Scale bar 100 μm . Z-stack shown as MAX intensity overlay, bright field displayed. I, J) Confocal microscopy images of ciPTEC (day 7, 33 °C) adhering onto the scaffold outlet pocket (I, scale bar 200 μm) and channel (J, scale bar 100 μm), stained with DAPI (blue, nuclei) and phalloidin (red, actin). Construct imaged in vertical position and cut for the channel cross-section. Z-stack shown as MAX intensity overlay, bright field displayed. K) Set up for continuous perfusion of the cell-free channel using an in-house made reservoir and a peristaltic pump. To enable a better visualization of the leak-proof pulsating, unidirectional flow, the channel was perfused with a blue dye.

a flow rate of 20 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. The leak-tight connection between the plastic tube and the hydrogel was monitored via visualization by adding a colored dye to the PBS (Figure 7K and Movie S5 (Supporting Information)). The flow remained stable and unidirectional over a period of 7 days, without leakage in the hydrogel inlet area.

3. Conclusion

In this work, a new thermoresponsive polymer was synthesized, showing tunable properties and allowing the formation via photo-cross-linking of stable hydrogels that undergo (reversible) isotropic shrinking in response to temperature increase of the aqueous medium in which immersed. This shrinking process was employed as a 4D fabrication strategy for cell-seeded hollow channels to reduce their diameters by 35–50%. Moreover, for the channels fabricated via volumetric printing, the shrinking process also showed its advantage for sealing the hydrogel inlet around a plastic tube, enabling leak-proof perfusion and, for the first time, cell seeding into channels with diameters below 200 μm . Compared to previously developed thermoshrinkable materials,^[31] PNH–MA remained transparent across all temperatures, facilitating imaging of the cells inside the channels. Moreover, PNH–MA hydrogels reached a maximum diameter reduction of 50% at physiological temperatures (33/37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), surpassing that of previous thermoshrinkable materials (maximum 35%)^[28–31,34,35] and comparable to shrinkable hydrogels that utilize other shrinkage triggers.^[26,38] In addition, PNH–MA polymer is one of the few reported low-viscosity resins successfully used for hydrogel volumetric printing of complex scaffold geometries. As a result, this study contributed to addressing the lack of diversity of (bio)ink materials in the volumetric printing field, as it laid the foundation for a new class of suitable resins. After applying a L-DOPA bioadhesive coating, ciPTEC adhered to the PNH–MA hydrogel surface and demonstrated high viability over a 14 days period, indicating that the thermoshrinkage process does not impair cell behavior. With this approach, ciPTECs were successfully injected into channels with diameter range between 100 and 170 μm , with possibility to apply continuous unilateral flow. It is important to note that the shrinkage of hydrogels may reduce the hydrogel mesh size, potentially hindering diffusional permeability and transport phenomena. Since diffusional permeability is inversely proportional to material thickness, it may be more advantageous to utilize tubular structures with very thin walls rather than channels within bulk covalently cross-linked hydrogels when investigating kidney transport phenomena, regardless of the swollen or shrunken state of the hydrogels. However, PNH–MA shrunken hydrogels showed a water content higher than 70% which likely still enables diffusion of relevant small molecules and proteins. The aforementioned achievements represent significant progress in advancing the field in vitro tissue modeling of channels by enabling the fabrication of cell-seeded perfusable microchannels to better investigate cell behavior in a 3D environment with dimensions more similar to physiological conditions. Volumetric printing allows for the fabrication of diverse geometries beyond hollow channels, offering new opportunities for tissue engineering and biomedical applications when using thermoshrinkable hydrogels such as the one presented in this study. Additionally, for modeling tubular structures, alterna-

tive techniques such as coaxial printing can be explored. This may require slight modifications to material properties or blending with another polymer to enhance printability.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: All chemicals were used as received and were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, The Netherlands) if not otherwise specified. All organic solvents were purchased from Biosolve (Valkenswaard, The Netherlands) and used without further purification. Solvents were dried using molecular sieves (3 \AA) at least one day prior their use. The synthesis of the PEG-based macroinitiator is described in the Supporting Information.

Synthesis of PEG Macroinitiator: As a starting material, PEG was functionalized with α -bromoisobutryl bromide to yield a bifunctional ATRP macroinitiator (Br–PEG–Br) according to previous protocols.^[43] Briefly, PEG 6 kDa was dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran (THF) under N_2 atmosphere at RT. Triethylamine (TEA) and α -bromoisobutryl bromide were added (10 equiv). This mixture was stirred overnight at RT. The formed bromide salt was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated under vacuum. Subsequently, it was dissolved in water and dialyzed (MWCO: 3.5 kDa) against deionized water at RT for 2 days. The product was freeze-dried and collected as a white powder with process yields > 95%.

PNH Synthesis: To synthesize the triblock copolymer PNH, NIPAM and HEA monomers were randomly copolymerized from a bifunctional PEG-based macroinitiator in a 90:10 molar ratio, respectively. A mixture of water and acetonitrile in volume ratio 4:1 was used as reaction solvent. ATRP was performed on ice under N_2 atmosphere in presence of CuBr (0.63 equiv to initiating site), CuBr₂ (0.42 equiv), and Me₆TREN (1.1 equiv), the addition of which immediately turned the mixture light blue. After 3 h, the reaction was stopped and the mixture was dialyzed (MWCO 14 kDa) against water at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and subsequently freeze-dried to yield a white powder (process yield range = 62–73%). Keeping the molar ratio between NIPAM and HEA constant, PNH polymers with different molecular weights were synthesized by changing the feed equivalents of NIPAM and HEA in relation to Br–PEG–Br, as illustrated in Table S1 (Supporting Information).

PNH–MA Synthesis: PNH–MA was produced from PNH by methacrylation of HEA terminal hydroxyl groups, based on a previously described procedure.^[55] Briefly, PNH polymer, 4-dimethylaminopyridine (catalytic amount) and TEA were dissolved in dry THF at RT. Methacrylic anhydride was added after which the reaction was stirred overnight at RT. MA and TEA molar ratios were kept fixed at 1:1. MA equiv to HEA units were changed depending on the desired DM, being 0.7, 1.2, and 2.5 to obtain PNH–MA with DM of \approx 35%, 55%, and 85%, respectively. Subsequently, the mixture was dialyzed (MWCO: 14 kDa) against water and subsequently freeze-dried to yield a white powder (process yield > 95%). For batches used for cell seeding, the dialyzed solution was sterile filtered (0.2 μm) and freeze-dried in sterile tubes with vented cap with a 0.2 μm filter membrane.

Polymer Characterization by ^1H NMR: All synthesized polymers (PNH and PNH–MA) were characterized via ^1H NMR spectroscopy using a Agilent 400 MR NMR spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, USA). Deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide was used to dissolve the samples. MestreNova v12.0.4 software was used to analyze and visualize the spectroscopy data. Sample peaks were referred to solvent peak (dimethyl sulfoxide-d₆: δ = 2.5, 3.3) and normalized according to PEG backbone (545.5H, δ = 3.50). Refer to Figure S1 (Supporting Information) for the chemical shifts of the polymer peaks and the equations used to calculate the amount of NIPAM and HEA units (N) in PNH, its total molar mass ($M_{n,\text{NMR}}$), the obtained NIPAM-co-HEA/PEG mass ratios and NIPAM:HEA molar ratios, and PNH–MA DM.

Polymer Characterization by SEC: The polymers were further characterized using SEC using a Waters 2695 Alliance (Waters Corp., Milford, MA) equipped with a differential refractive index detector. A mobile phase consisting of 10 mM LiCl in N,N -dimethylformamide was used to dissolve the polymer samples at 3 mg mL⁻¹. Analysis was performed by injecting

50 μL of sample solution into a PLgel 5 μm Mixed-D column for separation (65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, flowrate: 1 mL min^{-1} , run time 30 min). The column was calibrated with PEG calibration standards of narrow molecular weight (Polymer Standard Service GmbH, Mainz, Germany). Empower software was used for data analysis and calculating M_n and \bar{D} .

Polymer Cloud Point Temperature Measurement: The CP temperature of each polymer was determined using a FP-8300 Fluorescence Spectrophotometer (JASCO, Easton, MD) equipped with an externally cooled PCT-818 automatic 4-position Peltier cell changer. Samples were prepared in PBS at 3 mg mL^{-1} and loaded into 10 mm^2 quartz cuvettes. Light scattering at 650 nm at 90 $^{\circ}$ was measured while the solutions (stirred at 150 rpm) were temperature ramped from 4 to 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a rate of 1 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. The inflection point of increased scattering intensity was reported as CP.

MA Quantification via UPLC: The amount of MA in PNH–MA polymer (mmol g^{-1}) or cross-linked hydrogels was determined using a previously developed high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method.^[26] In short, 5 mg of polymer or dried hydrogel was dissolved overnight at room temperature in 2 mL of aqueous 0.02 M NaOH solution to hydrolyze the methacrylate esters. Next, 1 mL of acetic acid was added and the samples were injected into an Alliance Waters HPLC system equipped with UV–vis detection monitoring at 210 nm (Dual Lambda Absorbance, USA) and a Sunfire C18 column (column temperature: 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). An isocratic method was used based on eluent consisting of 15:85 acetonitrile: deionized water ($\text{pH} = 2$, adjusted with perchloric acid) with a set flow of 1 mL min^{-1} . The samples were referenced to a calibration curve of known concentrations of methacrylic acid. Concentrations were then calculated to yield the amount of unreacted MA per gram of polymer.

Hydrogel Formation via Mold Casting: PNH–MA polymers were dissolved in PBS and kept at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight to allow polymer dissolution below LCST. Prior casting, LAP was added to pregel solutions to reach a final concentration of 5 wt% PNH–MA (if not otherwise specified) and 0.1 wt% LAP. Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) molds were used to cast gels with different shapes by filling them with an adequate volume of pregel solution and irradiated using UV point source (Hoenle UV Technology, $\lambda = 320\text{--}500$) for 60 s, if not specified otherwise, with a light dose of 38 mW cm^{-2} . Importantly, pregel solutions were kept cold (in ice) until light irradiation was applied, if not specified otherwise. Different PDMS molds were used.

- i. Cylindrical molds ($\varnothing = 8$ mm , $h = 2$ mm , ≈ 100 μL) were used to test the shrinking process, degradation, sol fraction, cell seeding;
- ii. Cylindrical molds ($\varnothing = 8$ mm , $h = 3$ mm , ≈ 150 μL) were used for DMA;
- iii. Rectangular molds (10 $\text{mm} \times 15$ mm , $h = 6$ mm , ≈ 800 μL) were utilized to create hollow channels via mold casting by inserting two G27 needles (O.D. 413 μm) or three wires (O.D. 120 μm) per mold before pregel loading. Following UV irradiation, the needles/wires were carefully removed to produce straight hollow channels.

Hydrogel Characterization via Rheological Measurements: Rheological behavior of PNH–MA solutions was evaluated using a Discovery Hybrid Rheometer (HR)-2 (TA Instruments). Pregel solutions of PNH–MA with 0.1 wt% LAP were loaded onto a clear cover electrically heated plate with temperature control. A 20 mm parallel plate geometry was used to perform the measurements. An oscillatory time sweep of 10 min (5% strain, 1 Hz frequency) at a constant temperature of 6 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was performed. After 2 min, samples were UV-cured (Hoenle UV Technology, $\lambda = 320\text{--}500$) for 60 s. All measurements were performed within the linear viscoelastic region. Consequently, an oscillatory frequency sweep (0.01–100 Hz) was performed at 6 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to further characterize the UV-cured materials. The plateau values of storage moduli after photo-cross-linking (G' plateau value) were calculated by averaging the G' values in the time range between 3 min (1 min after the irradiation stopped) and 10 min of measurement. $N = 3$ for each tested condition.

Hydrogel Residual MA Moieties Quantification via UPLC: Methacrylic acid amount was determined by UPLC, cleaving it from pristine PNH–MA polymers or cross-linked hydrogels via base-catalyzed hydrolysis. Gels with different light exposure times (10, 20, 60 s) were tested (N

= 1). The following equations were used

$$\text{Residual MA content} = \frac{\text{ng (MA) in cross-linked hydrogel}}{\text{ng (MA) in pristine polymer}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MA consumption (\%)} = (1 - \text{residual MA content}) * 100 \quad (2)$$

Sol-Fraction Measurements: Immediately after forming the hydrogels via light irradiation (10, 20, and 60 s), hydrogel weights were acquired (W_{t0}). Then, the hydrogels were moved into vials, frozen, and freeze-dried overnight. The weight of the dry gels was recorded ($W_{dry(0)}$). Then, the dry gels were incubated in 1 mL of demi-water at RT, refreshing the water twice per day to remove unreacted polymer. After 2 days, the hydrated gels were weighed (W_t), then freeze-dried again overnight until dry, then weighed ($W_{dry(t)}$). The sol-fraction values were calculated using the following equation

$$\text{Sol fraction (\%)} = W_{dry(t)} / W_{dry(0)} * 100 \quad (3)$$

Characterization of the Shrinking Process Using Cast Hydrogels: The shrinking process of cylindrical PNH–MA hydrogels was assessed upon incubation in PBS at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, or at a different temperature when specified otherwise. At specified intervals, photographs of the immersed hydrogels were captured using a 1 cm grid as a reference. The images were analyzed using the Fiji ImageJ software, by drawing a circle around the cylindrical gel and measuring its area. Then, the respective diameters were calculated. To measure the cylinder volume, the height of the gels was acquired by positioning the hydrogel vertically on one side. $N = 4$ for each tested conditions. The relative ratio of shrunken diameter (D_t) over initial diameter (D_0) was used to report the diameter reduction. To express the shrinkage values the following equations were used

$$\text{Shrinkage degree (\%)} = 1 - (X_t / X_0) * 100 \quad (4)$$

where X was the diameter, area, or volume of the gel in its original dimensions (X_0) or at a determined timepoint (X_t). To calculate the x-fold reduction in dimensions, the following equation was used

$$\text{Shrinkage factor (X-fold reduction)} = X_0 / X_t \quad (5)$$

To assess the reversibility of the shrinking/swelling process, the gel dimensions were acquired after cyclical incubations of 24 h at 22/37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Stability Analysis by Weight Loss Measurements: The degradation analysis was performed by measuring over time the weights of cylindrical PNH–MA hydrogels incubated in PBS ($\text{pH} = 7.4$) at RT and at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. To acquire the weight, each gel was moved from the incubation liquid to a glass support, the weight was recorded using a microscale, then the gel moved back to the incubation liquid. Then, the water content (H) was calculated using the following equation

$$H = (W_t - W_{dry(0)}) / W_t * 100 \quad (6)$$

where W_t was the weight of the gel at a specific timepoint and temperature, and $W_{dry(0)}$ was the weight of the dry polymer present in the network, measured as described in the Supporting Information, sol-fraction method. $N = 3$ per condition.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis: To assess the compressive properties of the PNH–MA hydrogels, cylindrical hydrogel samples ($\varnothing = 8$ mm , $h = 3$ mm) were subjected to a force ramp at 2 N min^{-1} until 5 N at a controlled temperature via DMA (Q800, TA Instruments, The Netherlands). Both swollen hydrogels, maintained in PBS at RT after cross-linking, and shrunken hydrogels incubated in PBS at 33 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ or at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight were analyzed. The slope of the stress/strain curve in the 0–20% linear strain range was used to calculate the compression modulus of the samples.

Cell Culture: Human ciPTECs were originally isolated from human kidney tissue and immortalized as previously described.^[47] CiPTECs were cultured at 33 °C and 5% v/v CO₂ up to 90% confluency to maintain a cell proliferation state. For maturation, ciPTECs were transferred to 37 °C. CiPTECs were cultured in culture flasks (Greiner Bio-One, Alphen aan den Rijn, The Netherlands), using Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 without phenol red (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Paisley, UK), supplemented with 5 μg mL⁻¹ of insulin, 5 μg mL⁻¹ of transferrin, 5 μg mL⁻¹ of selenium, 35 ng mL⁻¹ of hydrocortisone, 10 ng mL⁻¹ of epidermal growth factor, 40 pg mL⁻¹ of triiodothyronine (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA), 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (v/v, Greiner Bio-One, Alphen aan den Rijn, The Netherlands). 1% antibiotic-antimycotic (Sigma-Aldrich, v/v) was added only during culture onto hydrogel surface. Medium was regularly refreshed after 2–3 days.

Cell-Seeded Hydrogels Obtained via Mold Casting: PNH-MA cylindrical hydrogels and hydrogels presenting hollow channels were cast as described above. The gels were transferred to sterile 24 and 12 well plates, respectively, and immersed in sterile PBS at RT. For sterilization, the hydrogels were exposed to 30 min of UV light and incubated overnight at RT (Group A cylinders and channels) or 33 °C (Group B cylinders) in PBS with 5% antibiotic-antimycotic (anti-anti, v/v). To apply the bioadhesive coating, a sterile-filtered L-DOPA solution (2 mg mL⁻¹) in TRIS Buffer (pH 8.5) was prepared and incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. Then, it was added to the cylindrical hydrogels for 3 h incubation at RT or 33 °C. When the coating exhibited a dark brown color on the hydrogel surface, the L-DOPA solution was removed, and the gels were rinsed 3 times with PBS. For the channels, the L-DOPA solution was manually injected into each channel twice (at 0 min and after 2 h) using a G27 hypodermic needle (Braun) or U-100 insulin syringe (Terumo) depending on the channel diameter (≈0.1 μL per channel). After 4 h after the first injection, when the channel turned dark brown, the channels were washed by injection of PBS. For cell seeding, ciPTECs were washed and detached with Accutase solution (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA). For the cylindrical hydrogels, 200k cells were added to each gel (0.3 mL per well). For the channels, a high-density cell suspension (4.5 M cells mL⁻¹) was manually injected into each channel (≈0.2 mL per channel). All samples were incubated at 33 °C overnight, then medium was refreshed to remove unattached cells. Immediately after cell seeding, the channels were flipped by 180° for 3 times (at 0 min, after 1 h, and after 2 h) to ensure homogenous cell adhesion onto the channel walls. As control group (2D control), 10k cells per well were seeded in a 96 well culture plates suitable for confocal imaging (Greiner). ciPTECs were cultured for 3 days at 33 °C (90% confluency) and for 11 extra days at 37 °C, except for the channels for which the time needed to reach confluency varied between tests and then cells were monitored for a total of 14 culture days. Medium was refreshed every 2–3 days by replacing the medium in the well and by manual injection of the channels. After the first incubation at 33 °C, all steps were performed using a heating plate set at 33/37 °C to maintain the hydrogel shrunken state.

Volumetric Printing: The pregel PBS solutions of PNH-MA with 0.25 wt% LAP were printed using a volumetric 3D printer (Tomolite by Readily3D). Before printing, the mixture refractive index was determined via a MA871 Digital Refractometer (Milwaukee). Ice-cold polymer solutions were loaded into adequate quartz vials and placed in the machine. Apparite software was used to load 3D construct models and control the process parameters. Various constructs were printed at an average intensity of 9.98 mW cm⁻² and optimal light dose was adjusted for each different geometry in the range of 85–200 mJ cm⁻², which translated to printing times of ≈8.5–20 s. The optimal light dose was defined as the dose that produced hydrogels most accurately matching the selected CAD model in terms of shape and dimensions. After printing, the objects were collected from the vial and washed thoroughly with PBS at RT to remove unreacted polymer. No further postcuring was performed. Alcian blue was used to stain the printed constructs to allow better visualization of the otherwise transparent hydrogels. Olympus SZ61 stereomicroscope coupled with an Olympus DP70 digital camera (Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions GmbH, The Netherlands) was used to acquire the pictures at 1x magnification of the 3D-printed hydrogels in PBS immediately after printing at RT and after incubation at 37 °C. The images were analyzed using Fiji ImageJ software,

using a picture of a 1 mm scale bar as reference. The shrinkage degree was calculated as reported above. For the channel diameter, 3 measurements per channel were taken.

3D-Printed Cell-Seeded Hydrogel Channels: PBS solution of 5 wt% PNH-MA 3.3 and 0.25 wt% LAP was 3D-printed by volumetric printing as described above using the CAD design shown in Figure 7 and in sterile conditions (scaffold height = 9 mm, diameter = 6 mm, channel diameter 250 μm). The light doses at which hydrogel channels showed the same diameter as the CAD model was chosen (light dose 95–120 mW cm⁻², printing time 9.5–12 s). Then, the printed hydrogels were washed to remove unreacted polymer and immersed in sterile PBS with 5% antibiotic-antimycotic at RT. For each scaffold, a plastic perfusion tube (outer diameter 1.5 mm) equipped with a rubber ring (inner diameter 1.5 mm, outer diameter 3.5 mm) was inserted into the inlet of the hydrogel. The entire construct was shrunken at 33 °C overnight to seal the inlet around the rubber ring (90% success rate). A luer-lock syringe was connected with a perfusion connector to the tubing inserted in the hydrogel scaffold. The L-DOPA coating solution (see above) was injected into the channels 3 times (at 0 min, after 1 h, and after 2 h) and incubated overnight at 33 °C. Then, after washing the channels by injecting PBS, a high-density cell suspension (5 M cells mL⁻¹) was injected twice (at 0 and after 30 min) into the channels. After cell seeding, the constructs were placed onto PDMS holders in sterile Petri dishes containing humidified paper tissues (dry chambers) and incubated at 33 °C for 2 h. To ensure homogeneous cell adhesion onto the channel internal walls, the scaffolds were rotated by ≈180° every 40 min for 3 times. Subsequently, they were immersed in warm culture medium and cells were cultured at 33 °C until ≈80% confluency. Then, the constructs were moved to 37 °C. Culture medium was refreshed by injection every 2–3 days. After the first incubation at 33 °C, all steps were performed using a heating plate set at 33/37 °C to maintain the hydrogel shrunken state.

Live/Dead Assay: At the desired days, ciPTECs cultured onto the several hydrogel scaffolds and in 2D control group were stained with calcein AM (live, 25 μL mL⁻¹, Sanbio) and propidium iodide (PI, dead, 50 μL mL⁻¹, Invitrogen) in culture medium (minimum 15 min incubation). Z-stack images (step size 10 μm) were taken using a confocal microscope (Leica Stellaris 8) and software Leica Application LasX. The temperature during confocal imaging was set at 33/37 °C using an Okolab H201 incubator box combined with a Okolab H201 T-unit. To quantify cell viability and surface coverage, the acquired images were analyzed using Fiji ImageJ software. Z-projections showing MAX intensity were made, converted to eight-bit, threshold was adjusted to render the image binary, and watershed was applied. Then, by using the “analyze particle” tool, the cells of the two separate channels were counted (particle size (μm²) for alive cells = 100-Inf, for dead cells 20-Inf). For the analysis of the channels, Z-projections of the half pipes were used. Cell viability and surface coverage values were calculated using the following equations

$$\text{Viability (\%)} = \frac{\text{Count alive cells}}{\text{Count alive cells} + \text{Count dead cells}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Area coverage (\%)} = \% \text{ Area alive cells} \quad (8)$$

For each condition, 1 biological replicate with 3 technical replicates for each imaging day was used. For the cell-seeded cylinders, 3 pictures of different areas of each gel surface were analyzed.

Immunocytochemistry: Volumetrically printed channels seeded with ciPTECs were fixed for 30 min with 4% v/v paraformaldehyde (Pierce, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) in PBS and permeabilized with 0.3% v/v triton X-100 in PBS for 30 min. Subsequently, the cells were exposed to the blocking buffer consisting of 2% v/v FBS, 0.5% w/v bovine serum albumin, and 0.1% v/v Tween-20 in PBS for 60 min. Actin filaments were stained with AlexaFluor 647 Phalloidin (A22283, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer overnight and nuclei with DAPI diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer for 8 min. All incubations took place at 33/37 °C to preserve the samples shrunken.

Immunofluorescence was examined using a confocal microscope (Leica Stellaris 8) and software Leica Application LasX. The temperature during confocal imaging was set at 33/37 °C using an Okolab H201 incubator box combined with a Okolab H201 T-unit. The channels were positioned vertically to image the outlet area, and cut to acquire the channel cross-section. Images were processed using ImageJ by making Z-projections.

Constant Perfusion Setup: A setup for enabling long term perfusion of the volumetrically printed channels was designed. The hydrogel scaffolds were connected to plastic tubing as described above. The setup reservoirs consisted of 10 mL glass vials with a detachable plastic lid. The inlet tubing connected to the hydrogel scaffold and an outlet tubing were inserted into holes made by puncturing the reservoir plastic lid, and then sealed using dental glue (Gi-mask automix, Coltene Whaledent). The hydrogel scaffolds were then immersed in warm PBS loaded into the reservoirs to prevent drying and maintaining the gel shrunken. Leak-tight assembly was tested by perfusing the channels with a blue food dye in PBS at 20 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. The inlet and outlet tubing were then attached to peristaltic tubing via luer-lock connectors and connected in a close loop to a peristaltic pump (Ismatec). The close-loop setup was transferred into a 37 °C incubator. The channels were perfused at 20 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ for 7 days with PBS.

Statistical Analysis: Results were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), sample size (N) equaled 3 unless otherwise specified. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, USA). Comparisons between experimental groups were assessed via one or two-way analysis of variances, followed by post hoc Tukey correction to evaluate differences between groups. Differences were found to be significant when $p < 0.05$ (ns $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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advanced in vitro modeling, kidney engineering, PNIPAM, temperature-driven shrinking, volumetric printing

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